

Projective Shape Analysis for Spatial Orientation in Virtual Environments

Mihaela Pricop-Jeckstadt^{1*}, Alexander Garthe²,
Vic Patrangenaru³, Robert L. Paige⁴

^{1*}Center for Research and Training in Innovative Techniques of Applied Mathematics in Engineering “Traian Lalescu”, National University of Science and Technology Politehnica Bucharest, Splaiul Independenței no. 313, Bucharest, 060042, Romania.

² German Center for Neurodegenerative Diseases, Fetscherstraße 105, Dresden, 01307, Saxony, Germany.

³Department of Statistics, Florida State University, 222 S Copeland St, Tallahassee, FL 32306, Florida, US.

⁴Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Missouri S&T University, 300 W 13th St, Rolla, MO 65409, Missouri, US.

*Corresponding author(s). E-mail(s): mihaela.pricop@upb.ro;

Contributing authors: alexander.garthe@dzne.de;

vic.prangenaru@fsu.edu; paigero@mst.edu;

Abstract

In this article, we apply extrinsic data analysis to the study of cognitive abilities evaluated based on the learning behaviour in the Dresden Spatial Navigation Task (DSNT) virtual navigational experiment. Our novel mathematical modelling of the spatial orientation and spatial learning is based on recent concepts in object-oriented data analysis like extrinsic mean and extrinsic covariance as well as novel statistical testing methods for random objects on manifolds. Finally, the allocentric orientation patterns in persons exhibiting mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and controls are detected for the first time via projective shape analysis.

Keywords: nonparametric statistics, projective geometry, extrinsic data analysis, neuroscience, spatial orientation

1 Introduction

55 million people were living with dementia in 2020 and it is a rapidly growing health threat. The number of those living with dementia is projected to almost triple to 135 million by 2050 ([1]). Our research brings an important medical and social contribution to healthier aging and to the understanding of some neurological processes fundamental to brain functioning by the interplay between neuropsychology, non-euclidean geometry, statistical methods and applied mathematics (see [2, 3]). Moreover, the application of our projective shape approach to spatial orientation goes beyond cognitive neuroscience towards automated orientation for cars, drones and satellites as well as robotics. Additionally, this approach links spatial orientation to quantum mechanics and cosmology via projective geometry (see [4, 5]). This setting might allow us to connect loss of time feeling in neurological diseases and loss of spatial orientation, and it might support the hypothesis that the brain functions as a quantum computer ([6, 7]).

A decline in spatial orientation is one of the earliest symptoms of dementia, as individuals lose the ability to navigate their environment ([8]). Spatial learning - the ability to move effectively from place to place - depends on reference memory, a form of long-term memory that stores stable information over time ([9]). The hippocampus, located in the medial temporal lobe, plays a central role in both long-term memory and spatial navigation ([10]). Seminal theories have proposed that it functions as a “cognitive map,” encoding the layout of the environment ([11, 12]). Evidence for this comes from both human neuroimaging, such as the enlarged hippocampal volume observed in London taxi drivers ([13]), and animal models. The Morris Water Maze demonstrated that rats can learn to locate a hidden platform using distal cues, providing a classic paradigm for allocentric navigation ([14, 15]). Allocentric strategies, which represent spatial relations independent of the observer’s position, rely heavily on the hippocampus, and patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or Alzheimer’s disease (AD) show marked deficits in such tasks ([16, 17]). Because the hippocampus is among the first brain regions affected in AD, impairments in allocentric spatial navigation represent a sensitive cognitive marker for early detection ([18]). A major advance in studying hippocampus-dependent spatial navigation in humans has been the development of virtual reality (VR) techniques. These approaches enable the translation of paradigms such as the Morris Water Maze into computerized 3D environments ([19, 20]). In such tasks, participants are placed in a virtual circular pool surrounded by distal cues but without local markers and are instructed to locate a hidden platform using a joystick. VR offers precise experimental control, objective tracking of behavioral responses, and strong ecological validity, as navigation performance in VR correlates well with navigation in real-world settings ([21, 22]). The Dresdner Spatial Navigation Task (DSNT), developed at Universitätsklinikum Carl Gustav Carus Dresden, is one such paradigm, grounded in the allocentric principles of the Morris Water Maze ([14, 23]). In the DSNT, participants must locate a hidden platform within one minute, guided by visual landmarks placed around the pool’s perimeter. Their trajectories are recorded as Cartesian coordinates and reaction times, providing rich quantitative data for analyzing navigational strategies. The task includes multiple trial types: pretests (assessing reflexes and familiarity with the

joystick), acquisition trials (assessing learning), and probe trials (assessing memory when the platform is removed). Testing spans two consecutive days: on Day 1, participants complete two pretests, one probe trial, and 12 learning trials with a fixed platform location; on Day 2, two pretests are followed by 12 learning trials in which the platform location is shifted after the fourth trial. Mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is widely regarded as an intermediate stage between healthy aging and dementia, particularly Alzheimer’s disease ([24, 25]). In the DSNT dataset, 54 participants were tested: 25 healthy controls, 26 with MCI, and 3 with minor dementia of the Alzheimer type (DAT). All participants also underwent standard neuropsychological assessments. Previous studies suggest that spatial navigation tasks can reveal distinct strategies—reflected in trajectory patterns—that are sensitive to hippocampal integrity and disease status ([8, 18]). Building on this evidence, our research examines how trajectory patterns in the DSNT reveal the interplay between spatial learning and spatial long-term memory, as well as landmark-based orientation—specifically, which environmental cues participants rely on when navigating.

2 Projective Shape Data Analysis

Projective shape analysis has its origins in the parametric statistics study of projective invariants. In this setting, objects are observed subject to an unknown projective transformation, and it is usual to use projective invariants for either testing for a false alarm or for classifying an object. For four collinear points, the cross-ratio is the simplest statistic which is invariant under projective transformations ([26]). A nonparametric methodology, via projective frames in arbitrary dimensions, was developed in the paper [27] on high level image analysis while [28] studies asymptotics of projective invariants and extrinsic and intrinsic sample means on projective manifolds for understanding of $2D$ scenes from their digital camera images. For a landmark configuration in \mathbb{R}^3 , "shape" deals with the residual structure of this configuration when certain transformations are filtered out. The non-shape components consists of size, position and orientation. Proportions, relative angles and the relative arrangement of parts are geometric features that belong to shape. Hence, spatial orientation as understood by the allocentric theory can be better studied in terms of projective shape. Additionally, projective shape is interpreted in terms of axial statistics, allowing a directional interpretation of the estimators.

Mathematically, the shape of a configuration consists of its equivalence class under a group of transformations. Here the group action describes the way in which an image is captured. For example, the pinhole camera model assumes that a $2D$ - image is the result of the projection onto the image plane of an ideal pinhole camera, where the camera aperture is described as a point and no lenses are used to focus light ([29]). If two different images of the same scene are obtained using a pinhole camera, the corresponding transformation between the two images is the composition of two central projections from $3D$ to $2D$, which is a projective transformation ([30]). The projective shape of an object consists of the geometric information that is invariant under different camera views. Moreover, these images differ only by a projective

transformation between themselves and from the original scene, even if the images are taken with different cameras. The pinhole camera model as a projective model can be extended to general dimensions. The homogenous coordinates are unique up to non-zero scalars in the elegant projective geometric framework. Therefore, the homogenous coordinates become points in projective spaces, and the perspective projection landmark model in the DSNT experiment may now be studied in terms of projective shape geometry from $3D$ to $3D$.

2.1 Projective shape space

We review in the following the mathematical results necessary to employ the projective shape analysis ([2]). In projective geometry two non-zero vectors x and y in $(m + 1)$ -dimensional numerical space \mathbb{R}^{m+1} are equivalent if they differ by a non-zero scalar multiple, where m is a abstract dimension of the image space. The equivalence class of $x \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1} \setminus \{0\}$ is labeled $[x]$. The set of all such equivalence classes is the projective space $P(\mathbb{R}^{m+1})$ associated with \mathbb{R}^{m+1}

$$P(\mathbb{R}^{m+1}) = \{[x]; x \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1} \setminus \{0\}\}.$$

and is often denoted as $\mathbb{R}P^m$. The projective space $\mathbb{R}P^m$ is topologically an m -dimensional unit sphere \mathbb{S}^m with the antipodal points identified, and can be represented as a disjoint union of ordinary and ideal projective points;

$$\mathbb{R}P^m = \underbrace{\left\{ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_m \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}P^m \right\}}_{\text{ordinary points}} \cup \underbrace{\left\{ \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ \vdots \\ x_m \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}P^m \right\}}_{\text{ideal points}}$$

In this framework for instance, a vanishing point in a three-dimensional image corresponds to an (ideal) point in $\mathbb{R}P^3$.

We now review concepts of projective transformations and projective shape space. If the calibrations of the cameras in the pinhole camera model are unknown, i.e. if there is no information available on the camera parameters such as focal length, angle between scene and film hyperplane, location of the camera, etc., then an image relies only on information about the scene which is invariant under projective transformations ([30]). Reconstruction of a configuration of points in $3D$ from two ideal non-calibrated camera images regarded as subsets in projective spaces with unknown camera parameters in absence of occlusions is known as the $3D$ reconstruction problem ([31]). This leads to the projective ambiguity of the $3D$ reconstruction problem: given two camera images of unknown relative position and internal camera parameters and two matched k -sets of labeled points in the projective space, find all k -sets of points in space as solutions of both $3D$ reconstruction problem. It could be proven in [32] that a landmark correspondence is needed to obtain a $3D$ reconstruction from any pair of $2D$

images. This leads to the concept of projective k -ads, as presented below.

A k -ad is an ordered list of k labeled points in \mathbb{R}^m ; it can be also regarded as a k -ad in $\mathbb{R}P^m$, via the standard affine embedding of \mathbb{R}^m in $\mathbb{R}P^m$ given by

$$p : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}P^m$$

$$x = (x_1, \dots, x_m) \rightarrow p(x) = [x_1 : \dots : x_m : 1] = [(x_1 \dots, x_m, 1)^T].$$

One approach to projective shape analysis ([33]), is based on the idea of a projective frame selected from the points of a finite generic k -ad in m dimensions. Such a representation has the advantage that it associates to the full set of projective invariants ([34]) of such a configuration one point on a projective shape manifold. The projective frame approach can be used to identify the projective shape of a planar curve in the context of a scene that contains four points in general position, that are not necessarily on the curve. The projective frame determined by such control points is used for registration. Ideally two registered images of the same scene should be identical; nevertheless due to registration errors and departure from a planar scene, they are different, and this raises questions about identification of the mean projective shape of a curve, testing for equality of such mean projective shapes of curves, etc ([35]). There are a few problems that arise in such a testing problem from curves in digital images. The identification of the actual curve in image processing, even from less noisy images, is first problem. Secondly, the curve registration problem presents challenges. Thirdly, the classical simple null hypothesis of equality of two mean curves, even when they arise from the same scene, is very likely to be rejected because of inherent registration errors; therefore a neighborhood null hypothesis for functional data is preferred ([36]). Finally once the test is established one has to dwell with intensive computational algorithms involved in functional data analysis.

An ordered list of $m + 2$ labeled points in $\mathbb{R}P^m$ is said to form a projective frame (basis) if they span $\mathbb{R}P^m$. An ordered list of $k \geq m + 2$ labeled projective points in $\mathbb{R}P^m$ are said to be in general position if the first $m + 2$ of these points form a projective frame. $G(k, m)$ is the space of all k -ads in general position in $\mathbb{R}P^m$.

A projective transformation $g = g_P$ of $\mathbb{R}P^m$ is the projective map associated with a nonsingular matrix $P \in GL(m + 1, \mathbb{R})$ and its action on $\mathbb{R}P^m$

$$g_P([x]) = g([x_1 : \dots : x_{m+1}]) = [P(x_1 \dots x_{m+1})^T]$$

The projective transformations of $\mathbb{R}P^m$ form a group, denoted by $PGL(m)$.

Division by the last coordinate yields a representation of a projective transformation g_P in terms of affine coordinates, as $v = f(u)$, with

$$v^j = \frac{a_{m+1}^j + \sum_{i=1}^m a_i^j u^i}{a_{m+1}^{m+1} + \sum_{i=1}^m a_i^{m+1} u^i}, \quad \forall j = 1, \dots, m$$

where $\det(P) = \det((a_i^j)_{i,j=1,\dots,m+1}) \neq 0$.

Two k -ads of points in \mathbb{R}^m have the same the projective shape if they differ by a projective transformation of \mathbb{R}^m .

The projective shape of a k -ad $X = ([x^1], \dots, [x^k]) \in G(k, m)$ is the orbit of X under the action α of $PGL(m)$ on $G(k, m)$, given by

$$\alpha(g_P, X) = (g_P([x^1]), \dots, g_P([x^k])).$$

Projective shape space $P\Sigma_m^k$, is the space of projective shapes of all k -ads in $\mathbb{R}P^m$ in general position $X = ([x^1], \dots, [x^k])$, such that $X = ([x^1], \dots, [x^{m+2}])$ is a projective frame :

$$P\Sigma_m^k = G(k, m) / PGL(m).$$

$P\Sigma_m^k$ is a manifold, homeomorphic with

$$\underbrace{\mathbb{R}P^m \times \mathbb{R}P^m \times \dots \times \mathbb{R}P^m}_{q \text{ copies}} = (\mathbb{R}P^m)^q$$

where $q = k - m - 2$. Projective shape analysis focuses on the properties of a configuration of colinear or coplanar points, as they are seen in a central projection by an external observer and it can be seen as a simplified analysis of vision in absence of occlusions. The image fusing method is based on extrinsic means of projective shapes of configurations of landmarks. Projective shape analysis is identified with multivariate (axial) statistics and it can be interpreted in the context of directional statistics. The projective space $\mathbb{R}P^m$ is topologically equivalent to a m -dimensional unit sphere \mathbb{S}^m with the antipodal points identified. Therefore, $P\Sigma_m^k$ is a manifold which is homeomorphic with polysphere $(\mathbb{S}^m)^q$ with the antipodal points identified. Hence, the extrinsic shape analysis has an elegant interpretation as a directional statistics.

2.2 Extrinsic Statistical Analysis in Projective Shape Spaces

The notions of extrinsic mean and extrinsic covariance on manifolds are at the center of our statistical analysis ([2]).

Let Q be a probability measure on (\mathcal{M}, ρ) , a complete metric space with a manifold structure of dimension m . If $j : \mathcal{M} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^N$ is an embedding, a minimizer μ_E of

$$F(x) = \int \|j(x) - j(y)\|^2 Q(dy).$$

is called the *extrinsic mean (set)* of Q .

A point x of \mathbb{R}^N such that there is a *unique* p in M for which $\rho_0(x, j(M)) = \rho_0(x, j(p))$ is called j -nonfocal where ρ_0 is the Euclidean distance in \mathbb{R}^N . \mathcal{F}^c is the set of j -nonfocal points.

A probability measure Q on \mathcal{M} is said to be j -nonfocal if the mean μ of $j(Q)$ is a j -nonfocal point.

A *projection* $P_j : \mathcal{F}^c \rightarrow j(M)$ maps any $x \in \mathcal{F}^c$ to the unique y such that $\rho_0(x, j(M)) = \rho_0(x, y)$.

The extrinsic sample mean is defined accordingly (see [37]).

Theorem 1. Assume Q is a nonfocal probability measure on the manifold \mathcal{M} and $X = \{X_1, \dots, X_n\}$ are i.i.d.r.o.'s from Q .

(a) If the sample mean $\overline{j(X)}$ is a j -nonfocal point then the extrinsic sample mean is given by $\overline{X}_E = j^{-1}(P_j(\overline{j(X)}))$.

(b) \overline{X}_E is a strongly consistent estimator of $\mu_{j,E}(Q)$.

Population extrinsic covariance matrix can be defined starting from the covariance of the embedded random object. Let $(e_1(y), e_2(y), \dots, e_N(y))$ be an *adapted frame to the embedding j* around $P_j(\mu) = j(\mu_E)$ i.e. it is an orthonormal frame field such that $(e_r(j(p)) = d_p j(f_r(p)), r = 1, \dots, m, \forall p \in j^{-1}(U_{j(\mu_E)})$ where $p \rightarrow (f_1(p), \dots, f_m(p))$ is an orthonormal local frame field on an open subset of \mathcal{M} . Let $\tan(v) = (e_1(P_j(\mu))^T v \dots e_m(P_j(\mu))^T v)^T$ be the tangential component of v . The *extrinsic covariance matrix* of the j -nonfocal distribution Q with respect to the basis $f_1(\mu_E), \dots, f_m(\mu_E)$ is defined as the covariance matrix of the random variable $\tan(P_j(j(X)))$ with respect to the j -adapted frame. Sample extrinsic covariance matrix is related to the sample covariance matrix of the embedded random object in the usual way.

The *sample extrinsic covariance matrix* of the j -nonfocal distribution Q with respect to the basis $f_1(\mu_E), \dots, f_m(\mu_E)$ is defined as

$$S_{j,E,n} = \left[\left[\sum d_{\overline{j(X)}} P_j(e_b) \cdot e_a(P_j(\overline{j(X)})) \right]_{a=1, \dots, m} \right] \cdot S_{j,n} \left[\left[\sum d_{\overline{j(X)}} P_j(e_b) \cdot e_a(P_j(\overline{j(X)})) \right]_{a=1, \dots, m} \right]^T$$

where $S_{j,n}$ is the sample covariance matrix of $j(X)$. $S_{j,E,n}$ is a consistent estimator of $\Sigma_{j,E}$.

For the projective space $\mathbb{R}P^m$, we will use the Veronese-Whitney embedding j defined in the following. $\mathbb{R}P^m$ can be equivariantly embedded in the space $S(m+1)$ of $(m+1) \times (m+1)$ of symmetric matrices via the Veronese-Whitney (V-W) embedding $j : \mathbb{R}P^m \rightarrow S(m+1)$,

$$j([x]) = xx^T, \quad x^T x = 1.$$

The V-W equivariant embedding of the projective shape space $P\Sigma_m^k$ $j_k : P\Sigma_m^k = (\mathbb{R}P^m)^q \rightarrow (S(m+1))^q$ is defined by

$$j_k([x_1], \dots, [x_q]) = (j([x_1]), \dots, j([x_q])),$$

where $x_s \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1}$, $x_s^T x_s = 1, \forall s = 1, \dots, q$ (see [28, 38]).

If $Y_r, r = 1, \dots, n$ are i.i.d.r.o.'s for which the mean shape μ_{jk} exists, it has a multivariate axial representation

$$Y_r = ([X_r^1], \dots, [X_r^q]), \quad (X_r^s)^T X_r^s = 1; s = 1, \dots, q.$$

Let J_s be the random symmetric matrix given by

$$J_s = n^{-1} \sum_{r=1}^n X_r^s (X_r^s)^T, \quad s = 1, \dots, q,$$

and let $d_s(a)$ and $g_s(a)$ be the eigenvalues in increasing order and the corresponding unit eigenvector of J_s , $a = 1, \dots, m+1$. Then the sample mean projective shape is given by

$$\bar{Y}_{j_k, n} = ([g_1(m+1)], \dots, [g_q(m+1)]).$$

From a general consistency theorem for extrinsic means on manifolds in [37], it follows that the extrinsic sample mean $[\bar{Y}]_{j_k, n}$ is a strongly consistent estimator of μ_{j_k} .

Theorem 2. *In the case of the VW embedding j_k , the sample extrinsic covariance matrix estimator $S_{j_k, E, n}$ is given by the $(mq) \times (mq)$ symmetric matrix $S_{j, E, n}$, with the entries in pairs of indices (s, a) , $s = 1, \dots, q$; $a = 1, \dots, m$, in their lexicographic order given by*

$$S_{j, E, n(s, a), (t, b)} = n^{-1} (d_s(m+1) - d_t(a))^{-1} (d_t(m+1) - d_t(b))^{-1} \cdot \sum_{r=1}^n (g_s(a)^T X_r^s) (g_t(b)^T X_r^t) (g_s(m+1)^T X_r^s) (g_t(m+1)^T X_r^t).$$

Hotelling's type statistics will allow us to apply a one-sample statistical test for random objects on projective shape spaces.

Let

$$D_s = (g_s(1) \dots g_s(m)) \in \mathcal{M}(m+1, m; \mathbb{R}), \quad s = 1, \dots, q.$$

If $\mu = ([\gamma_1], \dots, [\gamma_q])$, where $\gamma_s \in \mathbb{R}^{m+1}$, $\gamma_s^T \gamma_s = 1$, for $s = 1, \dots, q$, we define a Hotelling's T^2 -type statistic

$$T(\bar{Y}_{j_k, n}; \mu) = n(\gamma_1^T D_1, \dots, \gamma_q^T D_q) S_{j, E, n}^{-1} (\gamma_1^T D_1, \dots, \gamma_q^T D_q)^T.$$

Theorem 3. *Assume $(Y_r)_{r=1, \dots, n}$ are i.i.d.r.o.'s on $(\mathbb{R}P^m)^q$, and Y_1 is j_k -nonfocal, with $\Sigma_E > 0$. Let $\lambda_s(a)$ and $\gamma_s(a)$ be the eigenvalues in increasing order and corresponding unit eigenvectors of $E[X_i^a (X_i^a)^T]$. If $\lambda_s(1) > 0$, for $s = 1, \dots, q$, then $T(\bar{Y}_{j_k, n}; \mu_{j_k})$ converges weakly to χ_{mq}^2 .*

Remark 1. *Assume $(Y_r)_{r=1, \dots, n}$ are i.i.d.r.o.'s from a j_k -nonfocal probability distribution on $(\mathbb{R}P^m)^q$, and $\Sigma_E > 0$. An asymptotic $(1-\alpha)$ -confidence region for $\mu_{j_k} = [v]$ is given by $R_\alpha(V) = \{[v] : T(\bar{Y}_{j_k, n}; [v]) \leq \chi_{mq, \alpha}^2\}$.*

If the probability measure of Y_1 has a nonzero absolutely continuous component w.r.t. the volume measure on $(\mathbb{R}P^m)^q$, then the coverage error of $R_\alpha(V)$ is of order $O(n^{-1})$.

3 Spatial Orientation in Virtual Environments

A major progress in studying hippocampus-dependent spatial navigation in humans is due to the development of virtual reality techniques. This allowed testing navigational skills in various environments by enabling complete control over the complexity

of the task and objective recording of behavioural responses. Virtual environments can also be used to investigate spatial cognition since strong correlations have been observed between navigation in the real world and in the virtual reality. In this case, the assumed spatial navigation processing is the allocentric reference frame where the object locations are processed in reference to each other or fixed landmarks, independent of the observer’s position in the environment. The medial temporal lobe, especially the hippocampus, plays an important role in the allocentric spatial navigation, as indicated in many studies and confirmed by the poor performance of patients with AD and MCI in the tests requiring the use of allocentric memory. The Dresden Spatial Navigation Task belongs to the family of spatial tests conforming the allocentric principles of Morris Water Maze that is designated as hidden goal or hidden goal tasks.

3.1 The MCI data set

The mild cognitive impairment (MCI) is considered to be the link between cognitive changes in the healthy aging persons and those who are predisposed to developing dementia, usually the Alzheimer disease (AD). Hence, the decline in spatial navigation skills can be seen as a cognitive marker in diagnosing AD. The MCI data set, where a group of 54 participants, 25 diagnosed healthy, 26 diagnosed with MCI, and 3 presenting te symptoms of minor dementia of the Alzheimer type (DAT) performed this task, and were additionally subjected to a set of neuropsychological tests. The group consisted of 31 women and 23 men between 51 and 79 years old (mean age 69.1 years). Since the number of DAT patients is not high enough to constitute a separate group, they have been incorporated into the MCI group.

The individual planar curves are irregular (the step size around 10ms), and the starting point varies between trials. The final point (aka goal) and the scientific (topological) landmarks are fixed for all participants and all trials. The movement is constraint by the choice of the domain (circular in this case) and presents a drift in the direction of the goal (see Figure 1). When the participants reach the goal, they stop, while some participants can give up the test earlier from other reasons, like lack of concentration or motivation.

3.2 3D Extrinsic Projective Shape Statistical Analysis

A data point in $(\mathbb{R}^m)^k$ corresponding to the 3D– relative position of the k landmarks with respect to the path position is regarded as a k -ad in $\mathbb{R}P^m$, via the standard affine embedding of \mathbb{R}^m in $\mathbb{R}P^m$. For $m = 3$, the k -ad belongs to the group of p(rojective)-quaternions as an element of the projective space $\mathbb{R}P^3$. Moreover, the projective shape space $P\Sigma_3^k$ is homeomorphic to $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^{k-5}$. The extrinsic statistical analysis in the projective shape space $P\Sigma_3^k$ presented in section 2.2 is applied to the MCI data set. The projective frame consists of the most conspicuous landmarks i.e. the tallest five landmarks. First, we estimate the extrinsic means of the individual paths and the population extrinsic mean of the path extrinsic means that could be interpreted as the

population extrinsic grand mean corrected for the within extrinsic variation. The following step focuses on testing for differences between the population projective shape and the goal projective shape trialwise that could be seen as the effect of the long-term spatial memory as well as on testing for consecutive trial differences for each population that reflects spatial learning through working memory. The complete method is explained in subsection 3.3.

The field of quaternions, denoted by $\mathbb{H} = (\mathbb{R}^4, +, \odot)$ has the structure of a noncommutative field. The three-dimensional sphere S^3 inherits a group structure, called the group of quaternions of norm one. Since $\mathbb{R}P^3 = S^3/\{x \sim -x\}$, the operation:

$$[x] \odot [y] = [x \odot y]$$

is a well-defined *Lie group* operator on $\mathbb{R}P^3$, called the group of *p-quaternions*. The k -ads are represented as a $q = (k - 5)$ -product of p -quaternions since $P\Sigma_3^k$ is homeomorphic to $(\mathbb{R}P^3)^{k-5}$.

We use Euler's parametrization of quaternions to plot and interpret our results.

Euler's rotation theorem states that any displacement of a rigid body in three-dimensional space such that a point on the rigid body remains fixed, is equivalent to a single rotation about some axis that runs through the fixed point. Three of these numbers are the direction cosines that orient the eigenvector. The fourth is the angle about the eigenvector that separates the two sets of coordinates. To describe two successive rotations, quaternions must be combined using the non-commutative quaternion algebra. Using Euler's parametrization, we can identify the corresponding rotation (matrix) in $SO(3)$ corresponding to the p -quaternion as an unitary $4D$ - vector ([39]). Because rotation matrices are orthogonal, each column of a rotation matrix has length one and is perpendicular to the other axes. Therefore each column of a rotation matrix can be illustrated as a point on the surface of a unit sphere, which represents the position of the x-, y- or z-axis for that rotation matrix. Since each sphere represents one of the three axes, three spheres are required to fully visualize a sample of rotations ([40]). We interpret these angles as rotations with respect to each axes, resulting in three spheres corresponding to each axis. The "latitude" of a circle representing a particular rotation angle will be half of the angle represented by that rotation, since as the point is moved from the north to south pole, the latitude ranges from zero to 180 degrees, while the angle of rotation ranges from 0 to 360 degrees ([41]). The "longitude" of a point then represents a particular axis of rotation.

3.2.1 Landmark Learning in the DSNT Experiment

In the DSNT experiment, we compute the landmark projective coordinates in $\mathbb{R}P^3$ at each time point of the measured individual path. The extrinsic mean of the projective shape is estimated for each individual (the (empirical) path extrinsic mean) and each population (the (empirical) population extrinsic mean) trial-wise. Since there is not the danger of confusion, we omit the empirical term from now on.

Some probability distributions of the path extrinsic means of the projective shapes for the control and disease populations are displayed in Figure 2. The display of all 1752(= 2 · 12 · 73) distributions can be found in <https://drive.google.com/drive/>

[folders/19gzNFGcDlw336Y3zlb1IwcOiXUgwNoEX?usp=drive_link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/19gzNFGcDlw336Y3zlb1IwcOiXUgwNoEX?usp=drive_link). Additionally, the trial-wise trend of the population extrinsic means of the projective shape is displayed in Figure 3 for landmark 1, 3, 11, 15, 21, 71 separately for the control and disease. It looks like the population extrinsic means are highly concentrated over trials. Moreover, we centered the spheres around the Euler representation of the p -quaternions for the goal projective shape. Hence we can use the plots to interpret the orientations of the population extrinsic means with respect to the goal axes. The plots for all 73 landmarks can be found in https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1oI4SHDbnbkKH7uoXcel_l1bxx_y1dyJe?usp=drive_link.

The results of the one-sample test for the equality of the population extrinsic mean of the projective shape for each landmark, each trial, and each population with the goal projective shape are displayed as a black (reject the null hypothesis) and white (accept the null hypothesis) matrix in Figure 4. There are three patterns: only 1s, only 0s or 1s followed by 0s. This test suggests a classification of the landmarks in a class of "remembered" landmarks, a class of "forgettable" landmarks and a class of "unlearnable" landmarks. There is a remarkable difference between the control and disease pattern with no "remembered" landmark and mostly short time "remembered" (or "forgettable") landmarks for the diseased. Hence, this statistical test focuses on a spatial long term memory effect.

3.2.2 Between Trials Differences in Spatial Learning

Another research question is related to the process of spatial learning: are there any differences between the extrinsic means of the projective shapes of landmarks between two consecutive trials? The existence of statistically significant differences would support the theory that spatial learning happens between trials. The null hypothesis of equality of the population extrinsic means for two consecutive trials is expressed as the ratio between two quaternions. Since the quaternion multiplication is not commutative, all four possible ratios were computed and four hypotheses were tested. The results are displayed in Figure 5. The spatial learning looks complementary to the spatial long-term memory. There are statistically significant differences between trials for the landmarks that were "far away" from the goal projective shape. This might suggest an interplay between the spatial long term and working memory.

3.3 Projective Shape Analysis for Spatial Orientation PSASO Method

This approach does not model the vision directly. It is data-driven: it looks at the mean change of the landmark direction along the path, trial, population in the frame (basis) consisting of the 5 largest landmarks. Instead of focusing on the $2D$ path of a moving person, we turn the tables and consider moving landmarks. The dynamics is similar to the $2D$ movement of a point in a video along the frames except that we deal with a $3D$ image in this case. The main steps of the PSASO method are explained in detail in the following.

Step 1: Consider the virtual setting as a $3D$ landscape with $q + 5 = 78$ landmarks.

Compute the 3D-landmarks coordinates in the moving frame along the path for each individual, time point, trial, population as the coordinates of landmarks minus the path coordinates respectively minus the goal coordinates for the goal point $((x, y, z))$ of landmarks $-(x, y, 0)$ for path or goal points. $z = 0$ because the path is in the plane but we could also have nonzero z).

Step 2: Embed the 3D space into the projective space and compute the projective coordinates of the landmarks for each individual, time point, trial, population respectively for the goal (by adding a fourth coordinate equal to 1 to the 3D landmarks respectively goal coordinates). With the help of the V-W embedding, we can write the projective coordinates as an orthonormal matrix in $SO(3)$ (rotation) or as p -quaternions (quaternions on a 4D unitary sphere).

Step 3: Choose the projective frame (basis) with respect to which we make the registration of the landscape (consisting of the tallest 5 landmarks (largest z) in our case).

Step 4: Compute the projective shape of the landscape for each individual, time point, trial, population respectively for the goal with the help of the formula of factorization with respect to the projective transformations (see page 6). We obtain a probability distribution of projective shapes for each individual, trial, population. The projective shape contains information about how angles and relative arrangement of the landmarks change over path, trials and between populations. With the help of the V-W embedding, we can write the projective shape of the $q + 5 = 78$ landmarks ($(q + 5)$ -ad) as a product of $q = 73$ orthonormal matrices in $SO(3)$ (rotations) or of 73 p -quaternions (quaternions on a 4D unitary sphere).

Step 5: Compute the extrinsic mean of the projective shape distributions for each path and for each individual that we call the path extrinsic mean (use the eigenvalues and eigenvectors in the matrix representation).

Step 6: Compute the extrinsic mean of the path extrinsic means for each trial and for each population that we call the population extrinsic means (computed trial-wise). This is interpreted as an extrinsic grand mean corrected for the within variation along the path or as the between extrinsic means similar to the classical two-way ANOVA repeated measurements.

Step 7: Compare the population extrinsic means with the goal projective shape trial-wise by a one sample statistical test for the projective shape distributions. Results of the test are computed as a matrix with 0 (no statistically significant differences) and 1 (statistically significant differences). The matrices are plotted in Figure 4 for each population, where the x - axis represents the trial (1 – 12) and the y -axis represents the landmarks, and 0 is white and 1 is black. We can test every landmark separately by choosing a marginal approach.

Step 8: Compare the population extrinsic means between two consecutive trials by a paired statistical test for the projective shape distributions. Results of the test are computed as a matrix with 0 (no statistically significant differences) and 1 (statistically significant differences). The matrices are plotted in Figure 5 for each population, where the x -axis represents the 11 consecutive trials (2 vs 1, 3 vs 2 etc) and the y -axis represents the landmarks, and 0 is white and 1 is black. The test requires the computation of the ratio between the population extrinsic means in the consecutive trials. Since the quaternion multiplication is not commutative, we computed and tested for the four combinations that can be interpreted as $mean1 * (mean2)^{-1} = 1$, $(mean1)^{-1} * mean2 = 1$ (first row in Figure 5), $mean2 * (mean1)^{-1} = 1$, $(mean2)^{-1} * mean1 = 1$ (second row in Figure 5). The inverse of a quaternion corresponds to the inverse rotation. The product of two quaternions means a composition of two rotations. The order is important, since the angle of the final rotation is the same but the axis of the final rotation differs when we commute the factors. In our case, the products $mean1 * (mean2)^{-1} = 1$ and $(mean1)^{-1} * mean2 = 1$ have the interpretation that the mean rotation in the first trial compounded with the inverse of the mean rotation in the second trial is equal to the identity respectively the mean inverse rotation in the first trial compounded with the mean rotation in the second trial is equal to the identity. It is also possible to consider a theoretical hypothesis related to $mean2 * (mean1)^{-1} = 1$ and $(mean2)^{-1} * mean1 = 1$ with the interpretation the mean rotation in the second trial compounded with the inverse of the mean rotation in the first trial is equal to the identity respectively the mean inverse rotation in the second trial compounded with the mean rotation in the first trial is equal to the identity. We can test every landmark separately by choosing a marginal approach.

Remark 2. *The trend in testing for the equality of the population extrinsic means with the goal projective shape shows the long-term memory. It is interesting that we have white cells (no statistically significant difference) at the beginning of the experiment (trial 1) but only a few are still white until the end (trial 12) in Figure 4 showing ‘forgotten’ directions. It is also very clear that the diseased show much less white cells than the controls and no continuous white rows.*

Remark 3. *Effect size could be interpreted as a p -quaternion (with four coordinates like a complex number with norm 1) or as a rotation (as an orthonormal matrix or as a couple consisting of an angle of rotation and an axis of rotation, each column of the matrix was interpreted as a rotation with respect to the x -, y -respectively z -axis and the representation on the sphere in Figure 2 and 3 corresponds for each column of the matrix).*

4 Conclusions

An extrinsic projective shape analysis was applied for the first time to investigate the differences in the orientation patterns between a MCI and a healthy population in the DSNT virtual environment. PSASO offers a new intuitive and interpretable statistical method for studying and comparing spatial orientation strategies in 3D

Fig. 1: The individual $2D$ paths over 12 trials versus the $3D$ landscape with 78 landmarks

spaces. The data analysis was implemented with the help of the statistical software R and will be available as a free library.

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Fig. 2: The empirical distribution of the path extrinsic means and the population extrinsic mean for trials 2, 5, 6, 9, 11 and for landmark 1 (left:control, right:disease)

Fig. 3: The population extrinsic means of the landmark 1, 3, 11, 15, 21, 71 for trials 1 – 12 (left:control, right:disease)

Fig. 4: The one sample test for equality with the goal projective shape (left:control, right:disease)

Fig. 5: The paired sample test for equality of the extrinsic means of the goal projective shape between consecutive trials (left:control, right:disease)